

Mining code changes undermine biodiversity conservation in Brazil

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Protected areas (PAs) are vital for the conservation of Brazil's biodiversity (Barber *et al.* 2014). However, they are at risk of a downgrade in legal status due to economic pressures on natural resources (Bernard *et al.* 2014; De Marques & Perez 2014; Pack *et al.* 2016). Mining is one of the most urgent environmental threats in Brazil (Ferreira *et al.* 2014; El Bizri *et al.* 2016), with plans in place for a 10-fold increase in the number of mining projects in c. 8 years. If all were developed, the Brazilian territory occupied by mining would increase 23-fold in the near future. Currently, 12 697 projects covering 98×10^5 ha are planned within PAs. Licensing and exploitation of 53% of this land will depend on the approval of three bills that intend to authorize mining in areas where it was formerly forbidden. Here, we analyse the potential consequences of the approval of these new policies for conservation.

Brazil has a number of legal categories for land protection, including strict PAs, sustainable-use PAs and indigenous lands. Mining is only permitted in some sustainable-use PAs (named APAs and ARIEs from their initials in Portuguese; see Supplementary Material, available online). Today, 1195 mining projects covering 1.6×10^5 ha are established in these areas, while 367 projects covering 4.2×10^5 ha are working in PAs where mining is theoretically not allowed (Figs 1 and 2). The large impacted area in lands regulated as mining-free has various explanations. For some PAs, the law allows mining works to continue when they were approved prior to the establishment of the PA (IBAMA 2004). For the others, diverse misinterpretations of current law have led to improper mining concessions and subsequent judicial battles (Ricardo & Rolla 2006). In addition to direct habitat loss and the frequent destruction of caves (Ferreira *et al.* 2014; Sayuri *et al.* 2015), mining causes a range of secondary impacts. The massive migration of workers to low-populated areas, as well as the infrastructure associated with the project, further increases habitat loss and opens up intact wild areas to illegal forest colonization and exploitation (Laurance *et al.* 2009). Mining activity itself also has an impact beyond its frontiers: rivers downstream may be polluted (Castilhos *et al.* 2015) and threatened

by environmental accidents, such as the mining dam collapse that devastated the Doce River and the Southeast Brazilian coast in November 2015 (Escobar 2015). Finally, mining has often resulted in social problems and conflicts with nearby communities (Hilson 2002; Haslam & Tanimoune 2016), such as the confrontation between miners and the Cinta Larga indigenous tribe (Rolla & Ricardo 2013).

NEW BILLS MEAN 'CARTE BLANCHE' TO MINING IN PROTECTED AREAS

There are three parliamentary bills that consider the establishment of mining in PAs where it is currently forbidden. Each of the bills is directed at one type of PA. Bill PL37/2011 is proposed to allow mining in all types of sustainable-use PAs without restrictions on the percentage of the PA extension to be impacted. PL3682/2012 may allow mining covering up to 10% of each strict PA, and PL1610/1996 would allow the development of mining activities in indigenous lands without extension restrictions. PL1610/1996 is currently under consideration, while PL37/2011 and PL3682/2012 were recently retracted. Nonetheless, they could be brought back up at any time, especially given the scenario of political instability in Brazil. Moreover, mining enterprises appear to be preparing for the approval of the three bills. The government has recently received nearly 2400 applications for mining exploration or licensing within PAs in which mining is currently not permitted.

WOULD NEW POLICIES MAKE A DIFFERENCE?

In accordance with current jurisprudence, only mining planned at APAs and ARIEs could be licensed. There are more than 11 200 projects planned in these areas to date. Following their establishment, the area affected by mining in these units would expand 30-fold. This would increase the direct impact of mining on sustainable areas (Figs 1 and 2).

However, if the three bills pass, the mining impact in all other PAs could increase 13-fold (5 million ha) within 8 years, resulting in a total impact of 10 million ha by mining in Brazilian PAs (Fig. 2). The approval of PL37/2011 would open the possibility for extraction in sustainable-use PAs where mining is currently forbidden, in which 46 projects are planned. If this bill were approved, the development of these projects would increase the total impact of mining in these lands from the current 3×10^5 ha to 40×10^5 ha. The approval of

PL3682/2012 would imply the official release of strict PAs, where 1851 projects have already been planned. If these projects were developed, even considering the areal restrictions of the bill, the total impact of mining in strict PAs would expand from the current 0.7×10^5 ha to 8×10^5 ha. Finally, the approval of PL1610/1996 would mean a victory of mining enterprises over indigenous interests after a 20-year legal battle (e.g. Rolla & Ricardo 2013). The 114 million ha of indigenous lands that protect both biodiversity and indigenous rights would be available for mining without extension restrictions. To date, 541 projects have been planned in indigenous lands, meaning that the current impact of mining on these lands (0.2×10^5 ha) could rise to 6×10^5 ha.

Supporters of downgrading PAs argue that the total amount of land affected would be quite small compared to the large extents of Brazilian PAs (see Fig. S1). However, the average percentage of land impacted (Fig. 1) suffers from the fallacy of the average. There are many areas in which mining enterprises have not shown any interest yet, either because there are no exploitable resources or because benefits do not outweigh transportation costs due to geographical isolation. When averaging, areas with zero impact may overshadow large impacts on others, where mining already occupies up to 100% of the PA (Figs 1 and 2). However, impacts are relevant at the scale of individual PAs, as each one aims to preserve endemic biotas, landscapes or cultures of special interest (Schulman *et al.* 2007). Therefore, mining development and subsequent environmental damage may compromise species, ecosystems and human populations with restricted distributions. Moreover, our results only refer to direct impacts within project limits, so the real consequences of mining, including secondary effects, may be underestimated. In addition, the impacts shown here are added to those of illegal mining, which in Brazil accounts for up to 90% of artisanal mines (Barreto 2003). Such changes in the mining legislation may also hinder the compliance of Brazilian international agreements both to preserve 17% of its territory with effective PA networks and to reduce the extinction risk of endangered species by 2020 (Aichi goals; CBD 2010).

Here we have shown how changes in the Brazilian mining code may affect the PAs of the country in the short-term, considering projects that are in the planning phase. The velocity at which mining will impact Brazilian biodiversity in the mid-term is uncertain, although a change in the mining code may further stimulate the interest of companies in currently unexplored PAs. Mining is an important economic activity in Brazil (ICMM 2013), but

extending it across current PAs via any PA downgrading, downsizing and degazettement mechanism (Pack *et al.* 2016) is not compatible with the sustainable development of the country (Meira *et al.* 2016). New bills are neglecting the importance of PAs, as mining jeopardizes water resources and ecological services maintenance, climate change prevention and indigenous well-being and culture preservation. Mining companies are waiting for the open season to exploit new lands, while the parliament now has the opportunity to avoid further degradation of the PAs that may be the last refuge for Brazilian biodiversity.

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Figure 1. Impact of mining on Brazilian PAs today (black bars) and as planned for the near future under four legal scenarios (red, orange, blue and purple bars). The percentage land that is/could be impacted by mining is represented by means (white points), standard errors (boxes) and maximum values (whiskers); the average absolute impacted areas are shown by white numbers. Impact is defined as the spatial extent occupied by mining. Planned projects are estimated to be developed within 8 years. n = total number of PAs; PA = protected area.

Figure 2. Total extent of Brazilian PAs (grey) and area occupied by mining today (black) and as planned for the near future under four legal scenarios (from left to right): if any new law was approved (red); if PL37/2011 was approved (orange); if PL3682/2012 was approved (blue); and if PL1610/1996 was approved (purple). Each bar represents one single PA. Planned projects are estimated to be developed within 8 years. n = number of protected areas represented in the figure; protected areas with extents of 85 ha are excluded; PA = protected area. See Fig. S2 for more details corresponding to the grey rectangle in this figure.

REFERENCES

- Barber, C.P., Cochrane, M.A., Souza, C.M. & Laurance, W.F. (2014) Roads, deforestation, and the mitigating effect of protected areas in the Amazon. *Biological Conservation* **177**: 203–209.
- Barreto, M.L. (2003) Formalização da mineração de pequena escala (MPE) na América Latina e Caribe. [www document]. URL http://www.redeaplmineral.org.br/biblioteca/formalizacao-da-mineracao-a-pequena-escala-mpe-na-america-latina-e-caribe/at_download/arquivo
- Bernard, E., Penna, L.A.O., & Araújo, E. (2014) Downgrading, downsizing, degazettement, and reclassification of protected areas in Brazil. *Conservation Biology* **28**: 939–950.
- Castilhos, Z., Rodrigues-Filho, S., Cesar, R., Rodrigues, A.P., Villas-Bôas, R., de Jesus, I., Lima, M., Faial, K., Miranda, A., Brabo, E., Beinhoff, C. & Santos, E. (2015) Human exposure and risk assessment associated with mercury contamination in artisanal gold mining areas in the Brazilian Amazon. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* **22**: 11255–11264.
- CBD (2010) The strategic plan for biodiversity 2011–2020 and the Aichi biodiversity targets. [www document]. URL <http://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-10/cop-10-dec-02-en.pdf>
- De Marques, A.A.B. & Perez, C.A. (2014) Pervasive legal threats to protected areas in Brazil. *Oryx* **49**: 25–29.
- El Bizri, H.R., Macedo, J.C.B., Paglia, A.P. & Morcatty, T.Q. (2016) Mining undermining Brazil's environment. *Science* **353**: 228.
- Escobar, H. (2015) Mud tsunami wreaks ecological havoc in Brazil. *Science* **350**: 1138–1139.
- Ferreira, J., Aragão, L.E.O.C., Barlow, J., Barreto, P., Berenguer, E., Bustamante, M., Gardner, T.A., Lees, A.C., Lima, A., Louzada, J., Pardini, R., Parry, L., Peres, C.A., Pompeu, P.S., Tabarelli, M. & Zuanon, J. (2014) Brazil's environmental leadership at risk. *Science* **346**: 706–707.
- Haslam, P.A. & Tanimoune, N.A. (2016) The determinants of social conflict in the Latin American mining sector: new evidence with quantitative data. *World Development* **78**: 401–419.
- Hilson, G. (2002) An overview of land use conflicts in mining communities. *Land Use Policy* **19**: 65–73.
- IBAMA (2004) Instrução Normativa nº 31, de 27 de maio de 2004 [www document]. URL http://www.mma.gov.br/estruturas/pnf/_arquivos/in_ibama_31_04.pdf
- ICMM (2013) O setor de mineração no Brasil: fortalecimento institucional para o desenvolvimento sustentável [www document]. URL <http://www.opml.co.uk/sites/default/files/>

ICMM%20mining%20sector%20in%20Brazil%20case%20 study%20-
%20portuguese%20version_0.pdf

Laurance, W.F., Goosem, M. & Laurance, S.G. (2009) Impacts of roads and linear clearings on tropical forests. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* **24**: 659–669.

Meira, R.M., Peixoto, A.L., Coelho, M.A., Ponzo, A.P., Esteves, V.G., Silva, M.C., Câmara, P.E.A.S. & Meira-Neto, J.A. (2016) Brazil's mining code under attack: giant mining companies impose unprecedented risk to biodiversity. *Biodiversity and Conservation* **2**: 407–409.

Pack, S.M., Ferreira, M.N., Krithivasan, R., Murrow, J., Bernard, E. & Mascia, M.B. (2016) Protected area downgrading, downsizing, and degazettement (PADDD) in the Amazon. *Biological Conservation* **197**: 32–39.

Rolla, A. & Ricardo, F. (2013) *Mineração em Terras Indígenas na Amazônia Brasileira 2013*. São Paulo, Brazil: ISA.

Ricardo, F. & Rolla, A. (2006) *Mineração em Unidades de Conservação na Amazônia Brasileira*. São Paulo, Brazil: ISA.

Sayuri, L., Sugai, M., Ochoa-Quintero, J.M., Costa-pereira, R. & Roque, F.O. (2015) Beyond aboveground. *Biodiversity and Conservation* **24**: 2109–2112.

Schulman, L., Ruokolainen, K., Junikka, L., Sääksjärvi, I.E., Salo, M., Juvonen, S.-K., Salo, J. & Higgins, M. (2007) Amazonian biodiversity and protected areas: do they meet? *Biodiversity and Conservation* **16**: 3011–3051.

Supplementary Material – Additional Information

Brazilian protected areas and current mining legislation

Brazilian protected areas include conservation units and indigenous lands. There are two types of conservation units: 'strictly protected areas' and 'sustainable use protected areas'. 'Strictly protected areas' hold the maximum protective level and mining activities are explicitly forbidden within them (Law 9985/2000). 'Sustainable use protected areas' hold less restrictive conditions, and include seven different subtypes of protection figures: 'environment protection areas' (APA from their initials in Portuguese), 'areas of relevant ecological interest' (ARIE), 'national/state forests' (FLONA/FLOTA), 'extractive reserves' (RESEX), 'wildlife reserves' (REFAU), 'sustainable development reserves' (RDS) and 'private reserves of natural heritage' (RPPN). Mining activities are only allowed in 'environment protection areas' and 'areas of relevant ecological interest' (APA and ARIE). Finally, 'indigenous lands' are areas where the native populations hold all exploitation rights of the land they have traditionally occupied. The Brazilian Constitution of 1988 considers the possibility for the Parliament to regulate mining activities in indigenous lands, although laws of this nature have not been approved yet. Since the Constitution drafting process, the mining lobby has been trying to concretize this right arguing on the relevance of the mineral heritage of Brazil for the economic development of the country. Defenders of indigenous rights are opposed to mining in indigenous lands due to the high socioenvironmental costs of the activity. The first legislative initiative rose in 1989; while the bill PL1996/96 was created in 1996 and discussed on the parliament since then (<http://www.camara.gov.br/>). Thus, despite long-standing discussions confronting mining and conservationist interests since 1988, there is still no specific legislation to regulate mining in Indigenous lands.

Materials and Methods

Study area

The study area is the whole country of Brazil, focusing on regions where mining enterprises are established or plan to establish in the near future within protected areas (including conservation units and indigenous lands). We considered protected areas defined at federal, state and municipal spheres, and corrected for superposition among them giving priority by protection level.

Data origin and preparation

Geospatial mining data corresponding to the polygonal boundaries of mining projects registered until June 2015 was obtained from the National Mineral Production Department (DNPM) site (<http://sigmine.dnpm.gov.br/webmap/>). These polygons only represent the area in which the mining project is or is intended to be established. Thus, secondary adjacent impacts of mining activities are not considered here and we define 'impact' as the spatial extent of mining projects. Existing mining projects have an average extension of 354.5 ha; while planned projects (see below) have an average extension of 783.5 ha.

DNPM site also provided information on the licensing phase of each mining project. This information was interpreted according to the 'Miner's Guide' publication available at the DNPM website (<http://www.dnpm-pe.gov.br/Legisla/Guia/index.php>), which provides information on legal arrangements for exploitation of mineral resources, as well as on the necessary licensing procedures for each type of mining exploitation.

There are four different systems of licensing depending on type of mining exploitation:

(1) Permission and Concession System. This system is used for all minerals except those protected by monopoly (oil, natural gas and radioactive minerals), and applies to areas between 50 and 2000 hectares depending on the explored material. Contrary to other systems, it is needed a previous permission authorizing the applicant to search for a certain mineral substance (research requirement phase). Once conceded, the research occurs during the research permission phase. If the company is indeed interested after this search, it may ask for exploration permission (mining requirement phase). Projects in the

phase of research requirement are considered here as potential, meaning that they have lower possibilities to be accomplished than planned projects, and are therefore not included in the analysis. (2) Licensing System. This system is used for immediate use of substances in construction, such as red clay and limestone for soils correction (Brazilian Law 6567/78) and applies to small areas (maximum of 50 hectares). This is a much faster process compared to the 'permission and concession system', since it does not require a previous research. (3) Extraction System. This system is restricted to immediate use of substances in public constructions carried out directly by the government bodies of the Union, States, Federal District and Municipalities (Brazilian Decree 3358/2000), and applies to very small areas, with no more than 5 hectares. (4) ASM Permission System. This system applies to artisanal and small scale mining (ASM, Brazilian Decree 98.812/90), developed in areas up to 50 hectares. Each licensing system has a procedure with different nomenclature for licensing phases (Table S1). Considering the meaning of licensing phases at each licensing system, mining projects were reclassified as: 'potential projects' for projects that are in a phase of research requirement, 'planned projects' for projects that are in a phase of license requirement, and 'existing projects' for projects that are already conceded. By definition, potential projects have lower probabilities to be developed than planned projects. For simplicity, and in order to get more robust and conservative results, we decided not to include potential projects in our analysis. Thus, in this work we focus only in planned and existing projects. As a reference, we identified 1787 potential projects (vs. 1851 planned projects) in strictly PAs, 3315 (vs. 11240) in APAs and ARIEs, 1689 (vs. 46) in other sustainable use PAs, and 3809 (vs. 541) in indigenous lands.

Geospatial data on Federal conservation units and indigenous lands were obtained from *Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade* (ICMBio), while polygons on state and municipal conservation units were obtained from the Brazilian Ministry of the Environment (MMA).

Data analyses

The basic information for our analysis is the proportional and absolute overlap of the polygons of 'existing' and 'planned' mining projects with protected areas. The

proportional and absolute overlaps are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively. We defined four potential legal scenarios for the near future (see table 1 in main text), and calculated the area occupied by projects classified as 'planned' in the near future considering these four scenarios and the type of protected area the project was overlapping with. We also calculated the area occupied by projects classified as 'existing' within each protected area. In order to avoid overestimation of mining impacts, before all calculations we revised spatial superposition among PAs. In the case of superposition among conservation units, we eliminated superposed areas of those with the lower protective level. In case of superposition between conservation units and indigenous lands, we did not eliminate any area as there is not a clear hierarchy among them and we consider them to be affected by different bills and to have different conservation objectives. All numbers referring to number of projects or area of impact in the text are explicitly calculated for this work.

Estimation of time for a project to become accepted

In order to estimate the average time that a planned project would need to be conceded and thus become of class existing, we analyzed how long did this process take with other processes in the past based on DNPM process register. We selected the 10 more-recent existing mining projects occurring at each type of PA considered in the study (i.e., APA & ARIE PAs, other sustainable use PAs, strictly PAs and indigenous lands), summing up a total of 40 projects. We searched each of these projects at the DNPM official site (<https://sistemas.dnpm.gov.br/PortalMPF/Site/ConsultarProcesso.aspx>) using the process protocol number, and annotated the year that the process reached a planned phase and the year that it reached an existing phase for the first time (see Table S1).

The average time that a planned project needs to be conceded was estimated as the average of the difference between these two years, and resulted in 0.5 years for APA & ARIE PAs (range 0 - 2 years), 2.8 years for other sustainable use PAs (range 0 - 8 years), 3.4 years for strictly PAs (range 0 - 8 years), and 5.3 years for indigenous lands (range 0 - 12 years). The average estimate was 2.86 years. 95% of sampled PAs were accepted within eight years, while only two projects (5% of samples), that were settled in indigenous lands, needed 12 years to obtain permission. Considering that mining projects

in indigenous lands only represent the 3.6% of the total, it may be safe to assume that most planned mining projects may be conceded in a time-frame of eight years. It should be noted that this time estimation is based on past processes. Time of concession could be reduced in the future with the approval of other complementary bills that would facilitate and accelerate the licensing process (e.g., PLS654/2015, PEC65/2012).

Table S1. Licensing procedure systems in Brazil associated to different types of mining exploitation. Licensing phases for each system are shown with all possible nomenclatures considered at DNPM database. These phases define mining projects as ‘potential’, ‘planned’ or ‘existing’ (of which only the last two are considered in this study).

Licensing procedure system	Type of Mining Exploitation	Licensing phases of Potential Projects (not included in the analysis)	Licensing phases of Planned Projects	Licensing phases of Existing Projects
Lic.1 - Permission and concession system	all minerals except those protected by monopoly	Research requirement	Research permission; Mining requirement;	Mining concession;
Lic. 2 - Licensing system	substances in construction		Licensing registration requirement; Licensing requirement; Licensing;	License registration
Lic. 3 - Extraction system	substances in public constructions		Extraction registration requirement	Registration statement; Extraction registration
Lic. 4 - ASM permission system	artisanal and small scale mining (ASM)		ASM permission requirement; ASM requirement; ASM	ASM permission

Figure S1. Spatial distribution of protected areas and mining in Brazil. Existing (a) and both existing and planned mining projects (b) are shown in black; while each type of protected area is shown in a different color.

Figure S2. Detail of Figure 2 (corresponding to the grey rectangle in that figure) for APA & ARIE protected areas (a), other sustainable protected areas (b), strictly protected areas (c) and indigenous lands (d). See Figure 2 legend for further information.